

Original Article

Clinico-pathological characteristics of cervical cancer in Gombe, Northeast Nigeria: An update

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Abstract

Background: Cervical cancer is the fourth most common cancer in women worldwide and up to 80% of the cancer cases occur in Sub-Saharan Africa. **Objective:** Cancer of the cervix is a significant health problem and one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality amongst women worldwide. It is the most common gynaecological malignancy among women in the developing nations. This study aimed to review the clinico-pathological features of cervical cancer and provide an update on those cancers that were diagnosed in our centre. **Methodology:** This is a retrospective, descriptive study of all histologically diagnosed cervical cancer cases at the Department of Histopathology, Federal Teaching Hospital Gombe, over ten years (2013 – 2022). Records of diagnosed cervical cancer cases were retrieved from the Histopathology request forms and patients' case notes. Demographic data, clinical features, stages of the tumours at presentation, and histopathologic types and grades were extracted. The results were analysed using descriptive statistics. **Results:** A total of 701 gynaecological malignancies were diagnosed during the study period, out of which 308 cases were cervical cancer, accounting for 43.9%. The patients' ages ranged between 26 and 94 years, with a modal age group of 41–50 years. The three most common clinical presentations were abnormal vaginal bleeding, abnormal vaginal discharge and lower abdominal pain, while the commonest stage at presentation was stage III. Squamous cell carcinoma was the most common histological type and accounted for 82.1% of the cancers, while adenocarcinoma represented 12.3% and other less common subtypes constituted 5.6%. Treatment modalities rendered included surgery, chemo-radiation, radiotherapy and palliation, while most patients were lost to follow-up. **Conclusion:** Cervical cancer is the most common gynaecological malignancy, although this figure is lower than previous studies. There is an increase in the proportion of adenocarcinoma relative to the predominant squamous cell carcinoma.

Keywords: *Cervical cancer, Clinical features, Histological types*

Introduction

Cervical cancer is the fourth most common cancer and represents 7.9% of all cancer cases in women worldwide.^{1,2} In sub-Saharan Africa, where up to 80% of the cancer cases occur, cervical cancer is the second most common cancer in the female population.³ It is also the second most common type of cancer in women in the Southeast Asia region.⁴ Although there are disparities among European countries, cervical cancer is the 9th most frequent cancer among women and the 2nd most common cause of cancer deaths in women aged 15 to 44 years.⁵ Worldwide, there were estimated 570,000 cases and 311,000 deaths per year due to cervical cancer.^{2,6} It is one of the leading causes of cancer deaths among women in low and middle-income countries (LMICs).⁴ In Africa, sub-Saharan Africa is the region with the highest incidence of cervical cancer in the world, with concomitant high mortality affecting women at their

prime age.⁷ This is a source of great concern because cervical cancer is preventable and curable at low cost with currently available methods.⁷

In Nigeria, with 12,075 new cases and 7968 deaths due to cervical cancer, it is responsible for the highest number of incident cases and deaths in Africa, and one of the eight countries with the largest number of incident cases in the world.¹ Several studies from Africa and different parts of Nigeria have also indicated that cervical cancer is the most common gynaecological malignancy.⁸⁻¹⁴

Most studies on cervical cancer also reported similar findings regarding patients' biodata, clinical presentations, risk factors and modalities of treatment.^{6,7,10,12,15} Cervical cancer is predominantly seen in middle-aged, multiparous, unscreened women in a polygamous setting and of low socio-economic status. Other risk

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factors for the development of cervical cancer include immunosuppression, smoking and long-term use of oral contraceptives. Infection with high-risk human papilloma virus (HPV) has been strongly and globally associated with the development of cervical cancer.¹⁶⁻¹⁹

Most patients usually present at advanced stage with history of abnormal vaginal bleeding, foul-smelling vaginal discharge and lower abdominal pain. Depending on the stage of disease and availability and affordability of treatment facilities, modalities of treatment include surgery, chemo-radiation, radiotherapy and palliation.^{2,6,8,15}

Squamous cell carcinoma (SCC), along with its variants, is the predominant histologic type of cervical cancer seen worldwide.^{8, 12, 13, 20} Adenocarcinoma, also with its several variants, is the second most common histologic type. However, recent reports have indicated a rising incidence and proportion of adenocarcinoma relative to SCC, which may be attributed to an improved method of screening for early squamous lesions and an increase in HPV prevalence.²⁰⁻²² Other histological types of cervical carcinoma include adenosquamous carcinoma, adenoid cystic carcinoma and neuroendocrine tumours.^{20,23}

In an earlier study in our centre, Azeez OA *et al.*, analysed clinico-pathological features of cervical cancer over ten years (2010 – 2019).²⁴ In this study, the aim is to update the literature about the succeeding 3 years' data and to characterise the histopathological aspects of the diagnosed cervical cancer cases. Meanwhile, tissue blocks were retrieved which could be used to conduct molecular studies.

Materials and Methods

This is a retrospective, descriptive study conducted at the Federal Teaching Hospital, Gombe (FTHG) over a ten-year period between January 1, 2013, to December 31, 2022. The study centre is a tertiary health institution in Northeastern Nigeria that provides clinical services to the people of Gombe and neighbouring states.

All records of cases of histologically diagnosed cervical cancer were retrieved from the

Cancer Registry, Histopathology and Medical records departments. The records of yearly-diagnosed cases of gynaecological malignancies as well as total cancers of all histological types were collected from the hospital Cancer Registry. The reviewed cases of histopathological haematoxylin and eosin-stained slides were categorized according to the 2020 WHO classification of tumours of the uterine cervix.²³ In order to describe the diagnosed cervical cancer cases, characteristic features such as demographic data, stages of the tumours at presentation, treatment modalities and histopathologic types and grades were extracted. The results were analysed using descriptive statistics and displayed in frequency tables and charts.

Results

During the period of study, the total number of histologically diagnosed cervical cancer cases were 308, while the numbers of gynaecological malignancies and

total cancer cases were 701 and 3993 respectively. Therefore, cervical cancer accounted for 43.9% of gynaecological malignancies and 7.7% of total cancer cases.

The age range of the patients was from 26–94 years, mean age of 45.5±5.3 years and the modal age group was 41–50 years, as shown in table 1. Eighty percent of patients were para 5 and above (grand multipara), while only 5.5% were nulliparous; the remaining (14.5%) were para 4 and below. Of note, only 4.9% of cases (15 patients) had a history of previous Pap smear as a screening tool for cervical cancer. Two hundred and sixty-eight patients (87.0%) were not gainfully employed, while 69.5% of the patients were living in rural areas. It is noteworthy that only eleven of the patients (3.6%) were HIV-positive. However, none of the patients gave an account of smoking cigarettes.

Most of the patients had more than one symptom at presentation. The three most common clinical presentations were abnormal vaginal bleeding (91.9%), abnormal vaginal discharge (52.3%) and lower abdominal pain (23.0%). Other features included difficulty in passing urine/ obstructive uropathy (2.6%), dyspareunia (1.9%) and leakage of urine (1.3%) as shown in Table 2. Most of the patients presented at stage III (57.4%). Stages I, II and IV accounted for 4.2%, 17.0% and 21.3%, respectively.

The modalities of treatment offered were surgery (8.1%), chemo-radiation (20.3%), radiotherapy (17.6%), and palliation (54.0%). Among the patients who had radiotherapy or chemo-radiation, 84.1% had only 1 course/cycle of treatment. An additional 10.1% of patients had 2 cycles, while only 5.8% had 5 cycles of treatment. The treatment outcomes included cured (1.4%), survived 5 years (2.7%), lost to follow-up (89.2%) and died (6.8%).

Squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) was the most common histological type and constituted 82.1% (253/308) of total cases, with large cell non-keratinizing accounting for most subtypes of SCC (170/253). Adenocarcinoma accounted for 12.3% of the carcinomas of cervix, of which the usual-type adenocarcinoma represented the predominant subtype (27/38). Other less common subtypes of adenocarcinoma included villoglandular (3/38), serous (3/38), endometrioid (2/38), clear cell (2/38) and mucus-type (1/38). Adenosquamous carcinoma and adenoid cystic carcinoma contributed 4.9% and 0.6% of total cervical cancer cases, respectively, as depicted in Table 3. For squamous cell carcinoma, grade 2 (moderately differentiated) was the commonest histological grade and accounted for 52.6%; while grade 1 (well-differentiated) contributed 31.6% and grade 3 (poorly differentiated) represented 15.8% of the cases. For adenocarcinoma, grade 1 was the most common and constituted 51.4%, while grade 2 and grade 3 accounted for 37.8% and 10.8% of adenocarcinoma cases, respectively.

Table 1: Age distribution of patients with cervical cancer

Age group (years)	Number of cases	Percentage (%)
21 – 30	13	4.2
31 – 40	52	16.9
41 – 50	104	33.8
51 – 60	66	21.4
61 – 70	51	16.6
71 – 80	17	5.5
81 – 90	4	1.3
91 – 100	1	0.3
Total	308	100

Table 2: Clinical presentation of patients with cervical cancer

Clinical features	Number of cases	Percentage (%)
Abnormal vaginal bleeding	283	91.9
Abnormal vaginal discharge	161	52.3
Lower abdominal pain	71	23.0
Difficulty in passing urine	8	2.6
Dyspareunia	6	1.9
Leakage of urine	4	1.3
Leakage of faeces	2	0.6

Table 3: Frequency distribution of histological types of cervical cancer

Cervical cancer	Number of cases	Percentage (%)
Squamous cell carcinoma	253	82.1
Large cell keratinizing	80	26.0
Large cell non-keratinizing	170	55.2
Basaloid	2	0.6
Papillary-type	1	0.3
Adenocarcinoma	38	12.3
Usual-type	27	8.8
Villoglandular	3	1.0
Serous	3	1.0
Endometrioid	2	0.6
Clear cell	2	0.6
Mucinous	1	0.3
Other epithelial tumours	17	5.5
Adenosquamous carcinoma	15	4.9
Adenoid cystic carcinoma	2	0.3
Total	308	100.0

Discussion

In the last few years, the incidence and death rate of cervical cancer have been estimated to be on the decrease in most regions of the world, except for a few sub-Saharan countries where it is still the leading cause of cancer mortality in women.²⁵ This decline is mainly due

to increasing adoption of cervical cancer preventive measures and a relative surge in breast and other gynaecological cancers.²⁵ In our study, cervical cancer was the most common gynaecological malignancy, accounting for 43.9% of the gynaecological cancers, as well as 7.7% of total cancer cases. This figure is lower

than findings in previous studies done in Ghana and most parts of Nigeria and conforms with the observed downward trend.^{8-14,25} A more recent report by Lawal Qudus O, et al. in 2023 has indicated that in Nigeria, the numbers of incident cases and deaths from cervical cancer were 12,075 and 7968, respectively compared to 14,089 new cases and 8240 deaths as reported by Bruni L, et al. in 2015.^{1,26} Although some of the risk factors associated with the development of cervical cancer were observed in this study in concordance with several other studies, the relative lower figure in our findings could be partly due to low cases of immunosuppression and cigarette smoking, as well as the global increase in breast and other gynaecological malignancies. The establishment of opportunistic cervical screening services and an increase in adoption of implants (as opposed to oral contraceptives) in our society could also account for the declining incidence of cervical cancer.

The age distribution in this study is similar to that reported in several studies in Nigeria and other developing countries, emphasizing the fact that cancer of the cervix is a disease of the reproductive age group.⁸⁻¹⁵

Most women with cervical cancer present with more than one symptom; but the three most common symptoms at presentation in this study were abnormal vaginal bleeding, abnormal vaginal discharge and lower abdominal pain. The presence of other uncommon clinical features like leakage of urine, leakage of faeces and difficulty in passing urine are findings of advanced disease, as most women presented with stage III disease. The late presentation to healthcare facilities by patients with cervical cancer was mainly due to low socio-economic status, as majority of patients were not gainfully employed (87.0%) and were living in rural areas (69.5%). Similar findings were also reported by several other scholars.^{8,10,15,24,27}

The modalities of treatment offered in our centre were surgery (8.1%), chemo-radiation (20.3%), radiotherapy (17.6%), and palliation (54.0%). Among the patients who had radiotherapy or chemo-radiation, 84.1% had only 1 course/cycle of treatment. Patients who had surgery presented with early-stage I disease. Some of the patients with more advanced stages had chemotherapy and were referred for radiotherapy, while others had brachytherapy in our centre and were referred for external beam radiation. The high number of patients managed palliatively was due to their low socio-economic status, who could not afford the exorbitant prices of chemotherapy and radiotherapy, and opted for such treatment. The treatment outcomes included cured (1.4%), survived 5 years (2.7%), lost to follow-up (89.2%) and died (6.8%). These dismal treatment outcomes were due to patients' low socio-economic status and late presentation to healthcare facilities, as corroborated by other similar studies.^{10,24,27}

Despite the variations among studies concerning the

incidence of different histological types of cervical cancer, squamous cell carcinoma is the most common histological type, accounting for 70-80% of invasive carcinomas.^{8,12,13,20-22,24,26} Adenocarcinoma and adenosquamous carcinomas comprise 10-15% of all cases.^{18,20,22,23}

In this study, squamous cell carcinoma was the most common histological type and accounted for 82.1%, while adenocarcinoma contributed 12.3% of all cases of cervical cancer. Adenosquamous carcinoma and adenoid cystic carcinoma accounted for 4.9% and 0.6% of total cervical cancer cases, respectively. The predominance of squamous cell carcinoma is a worldwide phenomenon and confirmed by several local and international studies.^{8,12,13,18,20,22,24,26}

Similarly, the preponderance of the large cell non-keratinizing subtype of squamous cell carcinoma in our study is also in agreement with most studies, but lower than the finding in a Ghanaian study, which could be due to regional variation.^{8,21,22,28}

To corroborate the recent reports that there is global increase in the incidence of adenocarcinoma relative to squamous cell carcinoma cases attributable to an improved method of screening for early squamous lesions and an increase in HPV prevalence,^{20,23} this index study has observed an increase in the proportion of adenocarcinoma compared to previous studies both within and outside Nigeria.^{8,10,12,14,22,24} Although determination of HPV prevalence was not carried out in those studies, we have already collected archival tissue blocks of cervical cancer to conduct such molecular diagnosis.

The histological grading of invasive squamous cell carcinoma of the cervix is similar to that squamous cell carcinomas in other parts of the body, while adenocarcinomas, especially the usual-type, are graded based on architectural features, similar to endometrial adenocarcinomas.^{28,29}

Similar to observation in most reports that grade 2 (moderately differentiated carcinoma) accounts for the majority of cases,^{8,29,30} this study has also found out that 52.6% of cases of squamous cell carcinoma were grade 2 tumours. In this study, grade 1 adenocarcinoma (well-differentiated) was the most common and constituted 51.4% of the histological tumour grading. The predominance of tumour grade 1 in this study could be due to the large number of usual-type adenocarcinoma, but more studies are needed to confirm it. Tumour grading may convey some degree of prognostic information related to tumour sensitivity to chemotherapy or radiation therapy; it was observed that high histologic grade was associated with decreased survival in patients with cervical carcinoma that were treated by radical surgery and radiation therapy.^{23,31}

Several studies reported that adenosquamous carcinoma is a high grade and aggressive tumour with a poorer outcome, that tends to metastasize more often than common adenocarcinomas or squamous cell carcinomas.^{23,28,29,31} However, despite the reported

prognostic importance of tumour grading, some studies have reported no difference in survival for these three tumour types when compared stage by stage.^{28,31}

Conclusion

This study highlighted that cervical cancer was still the most common gynaecological malignancy in reproductive women in our community, although the figure is lower than previous studies and hence, is in keeping with the global downward trend. However, there was an observable increase in the proportion of adenocarcinoma relative to squamous cell carcinoma. Most of the women were of low socio-economic status, presented at an advanced stage and had palliative care. This is a major health concern that could be addressed by establishment of an organized screening program and the enrolment of such individuals in a health insurance scheme.

Contributions of authors

YMA assisted in the histopathology report of the sample and helped supervise the manuscript. AK conceived the idea, designed the analysis and drafted and wrote the manuscript. HUF provided clinical data. AIL assisted in the histopathology report of the sample. All authors provided critical feedback and helped shape the research, analysis and manuscript. All authors discussed the results and contributed to the final manuscript.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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